

ISic3581

Monumental fragment reading M·PA

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

marble

Object

tabula

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Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2019-07-16 - Jonathan Prag edited the file based on autopsy and study for 2017 edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated in 1971, in room 7 of the west portico of the agora

Coordinates

37.997856, 14.262463

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory 30590

Physical Description

Two joining fragments of an off-white marble, in differing states of preservation. Height 28.5-29 cm; width (max) 27.5 cm; depth 3.5 cm (top) to 4 cm (base). Fragment 1 (upper) preserves the upper margin of the stone, fragment 2 (lower) preserves the lower margin, although in both cases the edges are rough and weathered. Both fragments are broken to left and right.

Dimensions

Height 28.5-29 cm

Width 27.5 cm

Depth 3.5-4.0 cm

Layout

A single line of monumental letters is preserved across the face

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are clearly and regularly V-cut, but show a certain roughness in the chiselling. Traces of red paint are preserved in some of the strokes. The letters have elegant serifs, with a deep cut where two hastae join at the top (e.g. top of M, top of A). P is almost closed; M has vertical final hasta. A single triangular interpunct is preserved after the first letter.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 155 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: N/A mm

Text

1. [---]m · paṭ[---]

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation

Commentary

The first visible stroke on the stone is a slanting one, which makes clear that the first letter is an M. Only a single serif is visible upper right for the final letter, but such a downward sloping serif, vertically overlapping with the right hasta of the A preceding, cannot realistically belong to anything other than the left end of the cross bar of a letter T. Pat[---] could be part of patronus, pater, or patria all of which are plausible in the context of a monumental (building) inscription. Without this trace it would be tempting to read Pa[ccius] and a reference to a member of the family mentioned in ISic3572 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3572>] and (possibly) ISic3573 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3573>] and the Augustan coinage (RPC I, no.630-631, 633 [<http://numismatics.org/collection/2015.20.550>]).

Scibona proposed to treat this pair of fragments as part of the same text as ISic3580 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3580>] (the basilica fragment). The type of stone is very similar and the letters are of almost identical height and broadly similar form. However, the form and depth of the upper terminations of the letters M and A, the overall depth of the letters, the presence of red paint, and the differing profile of the stone (slightly taller, and thicker in its lower half) all challenge a direct association, even if the broad context and epigraphic type looks very similar.

The text is likely to belong to the first or second century AD.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645652

Bibliography

Prag, J.R.W., Tigano, G. 2017. Alesa Archonidea : il lapidarium. *Introduzione all'archeologia di Halaesa*. Palermo. At no.10

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Photo J. Prag courtesy Soprintendenza BBCCAA di Messina